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PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE EDUCATIONAL SOCIALISATION OF PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES (VISUAL IMPAIRMENT)

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the categories of individuals with visual impairments, their specific characteristics, the challenges they face in socialization and education, as well as the psychological aspects of inclusive education and social adaptation for young people with special needs. Furthermore, the article discusses several modern technologies that facilitate the integration of individuals with visual impairments into society and enhance their access to education.*

Key words: *disability, inclusive education, socialization, adaptation, psychological state, social protection, methodologies, visual ability, tactile perception.*

Introduction

According to the **World Health Organization (WHO)**, at least **2.2 billion** people worldwide experience **severe vision impairment or blindness** [1]. The issue of **inclusive education** and **social adaptation** for young people with special needs remains highly challenging. However, many educators lack the necessary training to effectively teach students with visual impairments, often failing to properly design and adapt educational materials to accommodate their learning needs.

Over the years, research in **child development, sociology, and special education** has led to the conclusion that children with visual impairments **thrive, develop, and achieve greater social integration** when raised in an **unrestricted and supportive environment**.

Through **locally accessible education**, facilitated by **well-trained specialists**, visually impaired children can engage in **shared everyday experiences** essential for a deeper understanding of the world around them.

As a result, the education of individuals with disabilities, particularly those with visual impairments, is an urgent issue. To address this challenge, **Uzbekistan** has developed a **Concept for the Development of Inclusive Education in the Public Education System (2020–2025)**.

This initiative aims to **enhance inclusive education, improve the educational system for children with special needs, and elevate the quality of educational services** provided to them.

The **Concept for the Development of Inclusive Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan** outlines the **goals, objectives, priorities, and medium- and long-term stages** of inclusive education development. It serves as the foundation for designing **programs and comprehensive measures** aimed at advancing inclusive education [2].

A key priority of inclusive education today is the **identification of new approaches** to the **socialization of visually impaired and blind students** within the educational process. In this context, understanding the role of **online socialization** is particularly significant, as it contributes to the evolution of the **general education system** and, specifically, inclusive education.

The **organization of education** for individuals with special educational needs is influenced by various factors, including **economic conditions, political structures, state social policies, religious influences, and national cultural mentalities**. These elements collectively shape the effectiveness and accessibility of inclusive education within a given society.

Methodology

This study examines the works of **M.Seligman, B.G. Ananyev, A.G. Litvak, A.I. Meshcheryakov**, and others, focusing on the **successful adaptation of young people with disabilities** to society across different periods.

The **socialization and protection of individuals with disabilities in Uzbekistan** have been analyzed by several sociologists, including **Z.F. Uzakova, D.Yusupov, A.Abdukhalilov**, among others. The author has reviewed and incorporated insights from their research to provide a comprehensive understanding of the subject.

Additionally, this study considers the **Concept for the Development of Inclusive Education in the Public Education System (2020–2025)**, analyzing key policies, perspectives, and statistical data relevant to the development of inclusive education.

Furthermore, the article examines **electronic platforms designed for visually impaired individuals**, evaluating their **features, functionalities, and distinguishing characteristics**.

Main part

For individuals with visual impairments, **social adaptation** is of primary importance. According to **A.I. Meshcheryakov**, an individual's engagement in **labor activities** serves as an indicator of successful **environmental adaptation**. He emphasized that the **adaptive capabilities** of individuals who are blind or deaf-mute should be cultivated from an early age through **structured exploratory activities** [3].

Similarly, **B.G. Ananyev** highlighted that human **sensory perception** itself becomes an essential means of acquiring knowledge about the external world and adapting to it. He argued that, alongside fundamental needs such as **nutrition and reproduction**, the sensory need for understanding one's surroundings holds **independent vital significance** [4].

Furthermore, **M.Seligman** introduced the concept of **“learned helplessness”** which describes a state in which a person with a disability, due to **excessive protection and dependence on others**, ceases to strive for success.

As a result, they may avoid not only routine activities but also new situations in which they have never attempted to act [5].

This perspective suggests that **isolating individuals with disabilities**, particularly those with **visual impairments**, within exclusive groups may **hinder their development** rather than facilitate adaptation. Instead of fostering independence, such isolation may inadvertently reinforce **learned helplessness**, leading to the opposite of the intended outcome.

According to **Z.F. Uzakova**, socialization is a **two-way process** that encompasses all **social interactions**. Through this process, individuals acquire and internalize a **system of knowledge, norms, and values** [6].

For individuals with disabilities, socialization plays a crucial role in fostering a sense of **belonging** within the community, thereby **reducing feelings of isolation and loneliness**. Moreover, it contributes to enhancing **self-esteem and self-confidence**.

Similarly, **A.Abdukhalilov** argues that there are **no significant socio-psychological differences** between students with and without disabilities. This **parity** provides a strong foundation for the **expansion and development of inclusive higher education** [7].

Based on this perspective, one of the most **promising strategies** for the **socialization of individuals with disabilities** is the **effective implementation of inclusive education**, particularly at the **higher education level**.

According to **D. Yusupov**, the **rights of individuals with disabilities** have been systematically violated for many years. He states:

“Although it may be convenient to study, work, live, and participate in cultural, recreational, and sporting activities in one place, it should be noted that deaf and blind people have been isolated from mainstream society for a long time.

Throughout this study, I argue that a major reason for such concentration was that it was easier for the Soviet government to control deaf and blind people through the institutions of the Society of the Deaf and the Society of the Blind, which were entrusted to indoctrinate communities with utopian communist ideology and mold Soviet citizens” [8].

This perspective highlights the historical marginalization of individuals with disabilities, reinforcing the notion that **every person with a disability is an equal member of society**. Therefore, addressing and eliminating **barriers to their socialization** remains a crucial and ongoing challenge.

Beyond socialization, **psychological factors** also play a significant role in the adaptation of individuals with **visual impairments**. **Psycho-emotional stress** tends to increase under conditions of **vision loss**, intensifying an individual's **perception of difficult life situations** and complicating the selection of **appropriate coping mechanisms**. This often leads to **internal psychological conflicts, social adaptation difficulties, and behavioral disorders**.

According to **A.G. Litvak**, individuals with **visual impairments** frequently experience **severe intellectual disorders, neuropsychic anomalies, and psychophysical infantilism**.

He emphasizes that studying the **psychological state** of blind and visually impaired individuals is particularly challenging due to the **diversity of conditions affecting visual function** - including variations in the **nature of the disease** and the **degree of impairment** of core visual abilities [9].

There are varying **degrees of vision loss**, ranging from **complete blindness** to **partial visual impairment**. **Absolute (complete) blindness** in both eyes results in the **total loss of light perception and color vision**. In contrast, **practical blindness** allows for **some residual vision**, enabling individuals to perceive **light, colors, contours, and silhouettes of objects** to a limited extent.

According to the **established classification**, individuals with **visual acuity between 0% and 0.04%** are classified as **blind**. This category includes both **completely blind individuals** and those with **residual vision** (i.e., visual acuity ranging from light perception to 0.04%).

Individuals with **visual acuity between 0.05% and 0.2%** are classified as **visually impaired**; they retain functional vision and can perform tasks visually, provided that appropriate **hygienic and ergonomic conditions** are met.

Students with **low vision**, or those on the **borderline between low vision and normal vision**, have a **visual acuity ranging from 0.5 (50%) to 0.8 (80%)** in their better-seeing eye. These students may not require extensive adaptive technologies but still face challenges in certain visual tasks.

As demonstrated above, the **visual conditions of individuals with blindness and low vision exhibit distinct differences**, which are summarized in **Table 1 (see Appendix)**.

A crucial factor influencing the **unique perspective of blind individuals on their disability** is **social support**, which plays a vital role in their **adaptation and well-being**. Social support encompasses a **broad network of stable social connections**, including **living and spending time with others, maintaining friendships, and participating in clubs or public associations**.

These interactions contribute to a **sense of belonging and emotional stability**, facilitating the **social integration** of individuals with visual impairments.

In the education of blind students, **“seeing” the world through touch and sensation** becomes a fundamental aspect of learning. As a result, it is essential to cultivate **tactile perception skills** from the **early school years**. From **preparatory grades to the ninth grade**, students undergo **progressive training** to enhance their **spatial awareness and mobility skills**:

- **Primary school (grades 1-2)**: Students learn to interact with their **immediate environment**, such as **small rooms, desks, and personal spaces**.
- **Grades 3-4**: They are trained to **navigate within classrooms, residential buildings, and school grounds**, and at this stage, they begin learning to use a **white cane** for mobility.
- **Grades 6-7**: Students develop the ability to move **independently outside school**, including **navigating streets and public spaces**.

A positive advancement in urban accessibility for blind children is the **installation of special auditory traffic signals** in certain areas. These **sound-based traffic lights**, particularly those placed near **schools for visually impaired students**, serve as an **essential safety feature**. Installed in **high-traffic areas**, these signals provide **clear auditory instructions**, helping visually impaired students **cross streets safely**. This initiative represents a significant step toward **ensuring the safety and independence** of schoolchildren with visual impairments.

A range of **measures** is being implemented in **Uzbekistan** to address the **educational needs of young people with disabilities**. To enhance **inclusive education in general education institutions**, the country is adopting **new approaches** to organizing an **inclusive education system**. Additionally, **regulatory and legal frameworks** are being developed to establish guidelines for the implementation of **inclusive education in general secondary education institutions**.

Currently, the **public education system** includes:

86 specialized schools and **21 boarding schools** for children with **physical or mental disabilities**, serving a total of **20,610 students**.

13,437 children with **physical or mental disabilities** who require **long-term medical treatment** receive **home-based education**.

Two specialized educational institutions provide **education and care** for children requiring **specialized learning environments**.

19 orphanages and **3 children’s towns** accommodate **2,577 orphans** and children deprived of **parental care** [10].

The **educational process for blind students** is uniquely shaped by the **limitations or complete absence of visual perception**, which significantly impacts **information exchange** [11, p.18].

Therefore, an essential aspect of their education is the **adaptation of educational materials and teaching methods** to ensure that students acquire **all necessary skills and knowledge**.

This process requires:

- The use of **tactile and auditory learning methods**.
- Teaching strategies that prioritize **auditory and tactile perception**.
- The application of **specialized technologies and materials**.
- The incorporation of **inclusive education approaches** to provide equitable learning opportunities.

By integrating these methods, **blind students** can effectively engage in education and develop essential skills for **social adaptation and independence**.

Assistive Technologies for Blind and Partially Sighted Students:

Blind and partially sighted students have **special educational needs** resulting from their **visual impairment**. These needs can be categorized into two groups:

1. **General educational needs**, which are common to all students with disabilities.

2. **Specific educational needs**, which are unique to individuals with **blindness or partial sight**.

To address these needs, various **general and educational platforms** as well as **assistive technologies** have been developed. Below are some of the most widely used tools:

1. Screen Readers and Assistive Devices

JAWS (Job Access With Speech) – A widely used **screen reader** that converts on-screen text into **speech**, enabling blind users to navigate and interact with **websites, documents, and software**.

NVDA (NonVisual Desktop Access) – A **free, open-source screen reader for Windows** that provides **speech and Braille output**. It is widely recognized for its **affordability and ease of use**.

VoiceOver (Apple) – A built-in **screen reader for Apple devices (iPhone, iPad, Mac)** that enables **auditory feedback and touch-based navigation**.

TalkBack (Android) – A **screen reader integrated into Android devices**, allowing **visually impaired users to access and interact** with their smartphones and tablets.

These technologies play a crucial role in **enhancing accessibility**, enabling students with **visual impairments to engage in education, develop digital literacy, and achieve greater independence**.

2. Educational Platforms and Learning Tools

Several **educational platforms and tools** have been developed to support **students with visual impairments**, enabling them to **access learning materials and develop essential skills**. Some of the most widely used platforms include:

Learning Ally – An **online platform** offering **audiobooks and learning materials** specifically designed for students with **visual impairments**. It provides a **large library of audiobooks and literature**, enhancing access to educational content.

Bookshare – A **digital library** that offers **free access to books** for individuals with **print disabilities**. Members can download books in **audio, Braille, or large-print formats**, facilitating **independent learning**.

Braille eReaders – Devices such as the **Braille Note Touch Plus** enable students to **read and write in Braille** while accessing **digital content and applications**. These e-readers enhance **literacy and accessibility** for individuals who rely on Braille for learning.

3. New Technologies for Visual Impairments

Innovative **technological advancements** have significantly improved **learning, mobility, and independence** for individuals with **visual impairments**. Some of the most notable innovations include:

Smart Glasses and Wearable Technologies

Aira – A service that connects visually impaired users with **trained professionals** through their **smartphones or smart glasses**. These professionals assist with **reading texts, navigating environments, and providing real-time descriptions**.

OrCam MyEye – A wearable device that attaches to glasses and utilizes **artificial intelligence to read text, recognize faces, and identify products and objects**, enhancing everyday accessibility.

Envision Glasses – AI-powered smart glasses designed to **describe surroundings, read text, and assist with various tasks**, making **daily activities more accessible** for individuals with visual impairments.

These **technological innovations** contribute to **greater independence, learning, and comfort** for people with visual impairments, allowing them to **actively participate in education, work, and social life**.

Recommendations

While we have previously outlined the **general educational needs** of visually impaired learners, the following are **specific instructional guidelines** that teachers should consider during lessons. These recommendations are particularly relevant to **language instruction** (e.g., an **English lesson**) but can be applied to various subjects.

1. Maintain Constant Auditory Cues

– Teachers should **verbalize their actions** to ensure students with visual impairments can follow along.

– For example, when writing on the board, the teacher should **read aloud** what is being written.

– This practice benefits **both visually impaired and sighted students**, reinforcing auditory learning.

2. Ensure Full Inclusion in Classroom Activities

– When dividing students into groups, ensure that **visually impaired students are equally included**, rather than being singled out for special assistance.

– Encourage **collaborative learning**, where all students interact and contribute equally.

3. Facilitate Social Interaction and Spatial Awareness

– To help visually impaired students **familiarize themselves with classmates**, implement structured speaking activities.

– For example, instead of simply responding "yes" to roll call, students can state their **favorite singer, football team, or actor**.

– This approach enables **blind students to identify peers and their locations within the classroom**.

4. Incorporate Tactile Learning and Realistic Materials

– Replace **visual aids** with **tactile learning tools** whenever possible.

– For example, instead of using **flashcards of objects**, provide **physical models** (e.g., a miniature car) that students can **touch and feel** to build **sensory-based understanding**.

– This method enhances **conceptual learning** and ensures **greater accessibility** for visually impaired students.

By integrating these **inclusive teaching strategies**, educators can create a **more accessible and engaging learning environment**, fostering **equal participation and comprehension** among all students.

Conclusion

The findings of this research demonstrate that **blind students**, while unable to see, possess **capabilities and strengths** in many other areas. Therefore, educators should make **necessary adjustments** to accommodate their learning needs while ensuring that they are not treated as **incapable of learning or participating** in academic and social activities.

It is essential to **create an inclusive environment** where visually impaired individuals feel **integrated into society**, not only within the classroom but also in **everyday life**. Inclusion should extend beyond education to **all aspects of social interaction**, ensuring that visually impaired individuals can **fully participate in community life**.

Moreover, **public and private sector representatives** should take **proactive measures** to address these challenges.

In particular:

State and non-governmental organizations must carefully consider the needs of **persons with disabilities** when developing **policies and regulations**.

Greater attention should be given to **legislation** and the **implementation of inclusive policies**, ensuring that they are **effective and practical**.

Targeted financial support through **social grants, government funding, and sponsorships** is crucial for the **social adaptation** of individuals with disabilities.

In **Uzbekistan**, there is a **significant gap in scientific research** on the **psychological aspects of socialization and education** for visually impaired and blind individuals. Addressing this gap is essential to developing **comprehensive strategies** that ensure **high-quality education** and **effective preparation** for professional and social life. Expanding research in this area will contribute to the **development of better training programs** and **enhanced support systems** for visually impaired students.

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Table 1 - Classification of differences in visual acuity in children with visual impairment

Category	Group	Visual Abilities and Limitations
Blindness	Complete blindness	Complete absence of visual perception, including the inability to distinguish between light and dark.
	Blindness with light perception	
	a) Incorrect projection	Unable to accurately determine the direction of light, limiting their ability to use light perception for independent orientation.
	b) Correct projection	Able to correctly determine the direction of light.
	c) With color perception	Can distinguish between light, dark, and colors, possessing some degree of visual sensory ability.
	Partial blindness	
	Visual acuity (in the better-seeing eye with optical correction) between 0.005 and 0.04	Can perceive objects visually, but visual images are of poor quality.
Low vision	Severe degree (visual acuity 0.05–0.09)	Significant impairments in visual functions, including narrowed visual fields, increased or decreased photosensitivity, difficulties in color discrimination, and compromised oculomotor functions. These children require training in both the traditional writing/reading system and the Braille relief-dot system.
	Moderate degree (visual acuity 0.1–0.2)	Visual distortions and challenges in visual control during movement. Many children exhibit monocular vision. Other impairments, such as reduced visual field, spatial contrast sensitivity, and oculomotor dysfunctions, may occur individually or in combination.
	Mild degree (visual acuity 0.3–0.4)	Permanent reduction in central vision, often accompanied by secondary visual complications, such as glaucoma.